

WHEN THE DARK CLOUDS DISAPPEARED: UNVEILING THE VOICE OF THE YOUTH BEHIND BARS

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When the Dark Clouds Disappeared: Unveiling the Voice of the Youth Behind Bars

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Abstract

This study aimed to analyze and understand the actual learning experiences of senior high school students who are incarcerated in Digos City District Jail – Male Dormitory. Unaware of much, this was undertaken to unveil the voice of the youth behind bars. The current study uses a single-case design and a purposive sampling of five (5) individuals and is conducted within a qualitative framework. The emergent themes from the transcriptions and qualitative template analysis of the audio-recorded interviews were documented. The study revealed the views and experiences of the student-inmates as well as their coping mechanisms and insights. Based on the findings, the following themes emerged: being locked in long years, encountering circumstances, trying to accept reality, full of uncertainties, longingness, being given the privilege, limited opportunities, full of unrequited dreams, praying unceasingly, motivating oneself, collaborating with others, set family as inspiration, study hard, change for the better, life inside the prison cell is hard, surpass everything despite difficulties, giving importance to education, uplift spiritual life, listen to parents, and reflect and do better. The study's findings could not generate a generalization of the participants' experiences. Other research approaches can also prove beneficial in assessing the severity of the issue and developing solutions.

Keywords: *guidance and counseling, views and experiences, coping strategies, insights, educational experiences, student-inmates*

Introduction

This study aims to explore the experiences of youth learning while incarcerated, the obstacles they encounter in their pursuit of education, and the arduous journey toward reintegration into society post-incarceration. By examining the role of education within correctional settings, this research seeks to understand how it can serve as a transformative tool, fostering personal growth and societal reintegration for ex-offenders.

Prison systems around the world are in crisis mode and unable to offer services like education at the level required by international standards due to recurrent overcrowding in jails. Prison education programs have been around since the 1800s, with an early emphasis on religious teaching. However, prison education did not make substantial progress toward playing a crucial part in rehabilitation and gaining greater acknowledgment for its potential impact on criminals until the 1930s. Any society that wants to prevent recidivism among ex-offenders must address the need to rehabilitate criminals (Boese, 2021; Panitsides & Moussiou, 2019).

For over a decade now, convicts at the NBP in Muntinlupa City, even those at the maximum-security compound or those who were given sentences of more than 20 years, have had the choice of taking part in a variety of vocational courses that they may utilize when they begin a new life. The Department of Education (DepEd) also provides Alternative Learning System programs so convicts who still need to complete their elementary and secondary education can take equivalency tests. However, many prisoners who participate in educational programs do so initially to get good conduct time off from their prison sentence (Mateo, 2019).

Equally important, one of my main responsibilities as a guidance mentor is assisting and guiding students in making academic and personal decisions. Students must get individual or group counseling, evaluate their potential and abilities, and coordinate student-related professional issues. The hardest part is figuring out how I am going to be able to give all of this to our youths who are now studying in jail and are Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL), as I know so hardly anything about their circumstances. It is challenging for me to create an intervention program, including how they were studying while simultaneously serving out their sentences inside the prison cell. This insight inspired me to start a qualitative single-case study that will help me understand more about student inmates. How were they able to view their experiences as student inmates? What is it like to be in confinement? How do they cope with the challenges they encounter? Moreover, what insights did they learn from their experiences?

Therefore, the research gap addressing the experiences of student inmates within local settings creates a breach in understanding their challenges and needs, undermining the effectiveness of campaigns and initiatives aimed at supporting them. Unaccompanied by exploring alternatives to restitution that are equitable and developmentally appropriate, interventions risk perpetuating inequalities and hindering rehabilitation efforts. Urgent action is needed to conduct a study delving into the personal views of student inmates behind bars, as this research could inform more tailored and effective approaches to meet their needs, ultimately striving for a more just and supportive environment for youth involved in the criminal justice system.

Literature Review

2.1 Student-Inmate Experiences

One of the most important rights is the right to an education for youths. Even more so for these young prisoners, being incarcerated does not negate their right to a good education, access to healthcare, a social life, or knowledge. The juvenile detention facility demonstrates a dedication to its mission of using education to improve the conditions of those who have received criminal convictions. It is anticipated that the education provided at the jail will be useful to young inmates once they leave the facility. The students had a positive experience in many ways since they received attention from the staff and performed well academically while attending jail school (Rosmilawati et al., 2019).

Besides, most of the youth—67%—said they were given all the knowledge they required in the first few days at the facility. Nearly one in two impoverished children, or 22%, stated they did not feel that staff would not ask for assistance if they were in need, despite most children, 87%, saying they felt that staff treated them with respect. Young people were interpreted as being most likely to say they would turn to their family if they had a problem and least likely to turn to an advocate, 5% of them (Youth Justice Board, 2019).

However, Juvenile sexual offenders differ notably from peers convicted of nonsexual offenses, displaying variations in delinquent behaviors, academic performance, and social issues. Both groups exhibit a negative association between school experience and delinquency, with academic struggles serving as a pathway to delinquency specifically the sexual offenders. Meanwhile, delinquency among general offenders is primarily correlated with socioeconomic elements and educational background (Tan et al., 2018).

Besides, prison schools present a rare chance for teachers and students to collaborate on pedagogy, offering a transformative experience that may be gratifying and demanding at the same time. However, even after completing a term, incarceration significantly limits an individual's life opportunities. Changing the conversation around prisons and prisoners and promoting a different criminal justice system is necessary to solve this. Tackling complex issues surrounding inmate reintegration post-release and reframing the conversation can lead to a more equitable and effective criminal justice system, promoting successful reintegration and reducing recidivism rates (Boese, 2021).

2.2 History of Education in Prison

As old as the jail system itself is education in incarceration. The evolution of the modern jail and its objectives of providing control, discipline, and punishment have been extensively discussed. Early debates revealed some overlap between the goals of education in prison and those of the current prison personal transformation and development of the individual, essentially a kind of what is now informally referred to as rehabilitation. Even opinions on the kind and amount of tuition that should be provided varied; the early proponents of penal reform desired education to be a part of their facilities to promote incarceration as a humane form of punishment (Behan, 2021).

However, the incarcerated population generally has lower average education levels compared to the general population. This educational disadvantage, compounded by the stigma of a criminal record, often limits their opportunities for employment and reintegration into society. Along with promoting personal development, self-worth, and a feeling of purpose—all essential for long-term rehabilitation and contributing to society—education also gives prisoners a sense of empowerment (Gibbons & Ray, 2021).

Also, a crucial distinction between the criminal justice and juvenile justice systems is that juvenile offenders should be rehabilitated rather than punished. The concept of rehabilitation originated from the Children Saver movement of the late 19th and early 20th centuries, based on the belief that children could be saved and redirected towards positive paths. This perspective has been reinforced over the years by the understanding that children and adolescents develop differently from adults, necessitating approaches that focus on their potential for growth and change rather than punitive measures (Krisberg, 2018).

Furthermore, a major distinction is that young people were considered impressionable and developmentally pliable because of brain plasticity. Evidence that suggests young people's brain development is still happening lends credence to this theory. Youths lack the emotional self-control that adults possess. Youth are less able to forecast the long-term repercussions of their actions and are more susceptible to external social influences from peers, relatives, and the environment. Although there is a wealth of studies on how susceptible young people are to social pressures, there are instances where this information is not included in the normative procedures used by many juvenile justice practitioners (Christenson, 2021).

2.3 Education as a Preventive Measure

Education and regular school attendance are essential deterrents to delinquency and engagement in the juvenile justice system; they can also have long-term beneficial consequences on employment and crime resistance. Additionally, many of these teenagers have a history of trauma, mental health problems, and specific educational requirements (Development Services Group, Inc., [DSG Inc.] 2019; Johnson, 2018).

In addition, some jails have independent schools on the prison grounds that are separated from cells and housing units and have well-stocked libraries and computer centers. The prison beams "lessons" into each cell, both within and outside the structure, to fulfill its duty to give education. While some offenders emphasize the importance of offering educational and psychological services, others are built on therapeutic communities (TCs) as institutions. Thus, the experience of imprisonment varies based on factors including security, confinement conditions, occupancy rates, activities and programs offered to inmates, their rights, the dynamic between inmates and prison staff, and educational opportunities (Behan, 2021).

Moreover, the educational needs of youth in the juvenile justice system are often complex and multifaceted, requiring tailored approaches that address both academic and behavioral aspects. Despite these obstacles, investing in educational support for these teenagers is crucial for breaking the cycle of recidivism and facilitating their successful reintegration into society. By giving importance to education in the juvenile justice system, we can provide youths with the opportunities and means necessary to lead better lives (Johnson, 2018).

2.4 Educational Transformation

Research suggests that adolescent detention education programs can enhance teens' social, cognitive, and life skills after their release from a juvenile correctional facility. In addition, findings showed that 52% of recidivating juveniles with special education were recommitted within a year of their release, and 37.6% of adjudicated juveniles with special education recidivated. The results of logistic regression in multivariate research showed that education did not significantly predict recidivism once other variables were considered (Ho & Rocheleau, 2020).

Nevertheless, it was especially challenging to assist them because of their circumstances. Teenagers in the juvenile justice system are legally entitled to a publicly funded education on par with that of their peers in regular public schools. Children who have been detained or placed in residential settings are unable to attend local schools. The literature that is already in existence offers details about the profiles of students in juvenile correctional education programs, the standards and quality of these programs, the availability of academic support, and the experiences of students (DSG Inc., 2019).

On the other hand, it is important to remember that actions, both self-efficacy and capability, assess a person's capacity to affect the desired results. These concepts serve as crucial markers for understanding not only an individual's intentions and behaviors but also the external factors that shape them. They draw attention to the connections between a person's opinion of themselves and the circumstances that either support or impede their activities and accomplishments (Quines & Pablo Jr., 2023).

2.5 Youth Support

Working as a teacher in juvenile detention facilities presents a multitude of challenges. Beyond the lower academic performance commonly observed among students in juvenile justice institutions, teachers often contend with emotional and safety concerns. These challenges may include managing disruptive behavior, addressing trauma-related issues, and ensuring the safety of both students and staff in a highly controlled environment. Despite these difficulties, educators play a vital role in providing support, guidance, and education to youth in detention, aiming to foster growth and development amidst challenging circumstances (DSG Inc., 2019).

On the other hand, youth specialists influence not just the lives of young people who are detained but also how they interpret their surroundings and how their treatment progresses. It is also possible for those who work in institutions with a correctional mindset to form stereotyped views of the people they oversee, which could serve to defend the way care is given and influence how the correctional officer sees themselves and their roles in the social system. In conclusion, it is critical to investigate the assumptions made by youth experts about how youths behave since these assumptions may affect how young people behave when they are discharged from the facility (Christenson, 2021).

Despite the presence of rehabilitative activities within the prison, Walden and Allen (2019) discovered that not all jail employees included rehabilitative practices in their routine tasks. Additionally, some staff members expressed doubts about the ability of young people to lead successful lives after release or made remarks about how difficult it would be to rehabilitate young people. Overall, a variety of factors could contribute to this result, including staff attitudes, the surrounding environment, climate, and culture, as well as local, state, and federal laws and resources (Walden & Allen, 2019).

2.6 Educational Rights for Incarcerated Youth

Youth in the juvenile justice system are legally entitled to an education that is on par with that provided in public schools. Despite having a statutory right to education comparable to those found in public school settings, the education provided to youth involved in justice in most states does not comply with federal and state guidelines. Regional studies have shown that the academic attainment of youth participating in the legal system is extremely low, even though it has yet to be discovered at the national level. Delinquency among adolescents frequently leads to lower academic success, school dropout, and recidivism (DSG Inc., 2019).

Also, through the lens of the educational resilience paradigm, on-time high school graduation becomes a measure of success. These academics contend that, despite unfavorable experiences, some children can overcome these challenges and attain achievements. The educational resilience framework supports this idea. Furthermore, a higher level of self-efficacy did not enhance the likelihood of returning after a previous dropout to finish high school or earn an alternate credential (Rosen et al., 2019).

Finally, the European Prison Rules Rule 28, which states that every prison shall seek to provide all prisoners with access to education plans that are as comprehensive as is reasonably possible and that consider their objectives while also meeting their specific demands, gives a detailed overview of what national governments and specific institutions should be expected to do. Priority will be given to inmates who have a foundational or vocational education as well as those who are read and numerate. Education must be valued equally to labor inside the jail system, and participants in it cannot be penalized in any way, either financially or otherwise (Council of Europe,

2020).

Methodology

This study employed descriptive qualitative techniques in this single-case research study. Furthermore, qualitative research focuses on the meanings derived from human experiences. As a result, the "yes" or "no" questions that directed this study remained unanswered. Instead, the researcher wanted to comprehend how the individuals felt about the ordinary phenomena. Although individual human experiences cannot be generalized, qualitative research focuses more on the meaning of these experiences than quantitative approaches do (Bhattacharya, 2017).

In this case, the primary method for collecting data was semi-structured interviews. The researchers will interview the advisor overseeing the students in the jail learning environment. Upon request from the student participant, the name, section, and gender of the participant in this study will all be treated with confidentiality. Additionally, information was gathered from nonverbal observations, profile questionnaires, prison records, staff interviews, and informal discussions. The eligibility criteria for the study were established to draw research participants actively enrolled in educational programs while incarcerated (Halkias et al., 2022).

Before starting the study, I decided on the events in which she was most interested and identified the potential participants. I selected the five youths using a purposive sampling technique based on predetermined criteria relevant to the research topic. The purposive sampling technique was employed, wherein the researchers used their judgment to pick a sample that they considered, based on prior knowledge, would give the necessary data (Fraenkel et al., 2023).

Furthermore, I purposely included five participants among the student-inmates currently attending Mary Mediatrix of All Graces Academy, Inc. At the same time, they are detained and are part of the Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) in Digos City District Jail Male Dormitory. Upon preparing the list, I prepared a letter of permission to the school administrator, teacher-in-charge, and wardens of Digos City District Jail, where the identified participants were based. I also sought out and invited a licensed guidance counselor since she was concerned that this interview would reopen old wounds or result in anxiety because of her understanding of the challenges encountered in jail. Afterward, information was collected to determine which individuals would be eligible for the phenomenon under study.

Before starting the data-gathering process, I had permission from RMMC—ERC, the Graduate School Dean, my professor, and my adviser to collect data for the study. Afterward, since it is a private educational setting, authorization was requested from the Office of the School Administration. The responsible teacher, the Digos City District Jail wardens, and a licensed guidance counselor were approached.

After the interview, participants will interact with a licensed guidance counselor for counseling. They were encouraged to share their stories to inspire other youths to avoid imprisonment. While others are tales of hopelessness some of their stories can act as a source of inspiration for the youth. The research's coping mechanism might comfort them even though student inmates are fully aware of the likelihood of hardships while they are in bars. Finding a way to begin "solving" a problematic situation can be challenging when it is already stressful. They can tolerate, reduce, and handle stressful events in life using coping mechanisms (Cooks-Campbell, 2022).

In conclusion, I ensured that the listening principles were observed during the data collection and that the participants were free to express their emotions. Also, through one-on-one interviews, I tried to demonstrate that I was present with them the whole time they shared their experiences. Of course, throughout their reveal, there were certain things I wanted to make clear, but I made sure to do it politely and repeatedly to win their confidence. Their audio recordings were played to them to assess if there were any issues they wanted to eliminate to strengthen trust and confidence. Even the recorded notes were presented to them for review and confirmation (Tavory, 2020).

Results and Discussion

The study findings are presented in themes or categories in tables following the order in which the research questions had been posed. It allows readers to perceive many points of view readily. The researcher ensured the results were valid and reliable and chose authentic transcripts with an English translation to support key ideas.

In this part, the participants' descriptions of their experiences as student inmates are analyzed, their strategies for overcoming difficulties inside the prison and the insights they have gained from their experiences. One of the most often used qualitative analysis methods is thematic analysis.

Table 1. Views of the Participants Experiences as Student-Inmates

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Looked for almost three years.	
Locked up for five years.	
Locked for seven years.	Locked in Long Years
Locked for four years.	
The trial was postponed.	Encountered Circumstances

The judge was replaced.	
Financial problem.	
A misunderstanding happened.	
Encountered bullying.	
Accept things as they are.	
Left with no choice, acceptance is a must.	
Change for the better.	
Accept what happened.	Acceptance of Reality
Accept the sin that we committed.	
Accept being at fault.	
In denial.	
Felt hopeless.	
There is no assurance to be freed from being locked up.	
No idea of the things that might happen.	Full of uncertainties
Uncertain schedule of court trials.	
The future is not a guarantee.	
Missed their family.	
Became sad.	
I felt stressed because of being far away from home.	Longingness for their loved ones
Unable to see their family.	
No contact with the family during a pandemic.	
Availed ALS program.	
Able to be educated.	Given Privelege
Handle religious activity.	
Held prayer sessions.	
Limited resources.	
Unable to use technology.	
Unable to do research.	Limited Opportunities
I missed the opportunity to be with the family.	
Being bashed because of gender.	
Felt unaccepted because of being gay.	
He could have finished his education.	
Could have become as seaman.	
I could have done more.	Full of Unrequited Dreams
Could have become as older.	
I could have been to Japan and worked.	
Could have helped the family.	

Everyone was also awaiting the judge's decision on their case. A judge must consider four key considerations when deciding how much time a person will spend in jail. Retribution (punishing the offender for their wrongdoing), rehabilitation (altering problematic behaviour), safety (keeping dangers outside of the community), and deterrence (ensuring that they and others are scared off from breaching the law in the future) are the four main types of punishment (Lufkin, 2018).

Ideally, having a positive outlook and taking responsibility for your actions to overcome obstacles and achieve your goals is crucial. It applies to those inside and outside prison walls, as everyone faces challenges in life. Ultimately, it is up to everyone to choose how they will respond to these challenges and whether they will let them define their lives or use them as opportunities for growth and improvement (Lufkin, 2018; Paglia, 2021).

Given the fact that life can sometimes put us in situations we can't change. With circumstances that are out of your control, radical acceptance is embracing reality as it is. It doesn't imply that you're okay with the circumstance, that you're giving up, or that it's not unpleasant. Consider what it would be like to accept reality, even if you're having trouble doing so. If you just accepted things as they are, how would you behave? What would be your course of action? It might be helpful to alter your acts and behaviours to show "pretend acceptance" to change your thinking (The Village Family Service Center, 2021).

Over and above that, living in an uncertain world can cause tension, anxiety, and a sense of helplessness as we naturally seek security and control over our lives. Fear and uncertainty can lead to emotional exhaustion and a cycle of negative thoughts about the future (Robinson & Smith, 2023).

Yet, privilege encompasses the social advantages, benefits, and status that certain groups enjoy due to their social identity. It includes benefits resulting from the repression and persecution of minority groups by those in power or a majority. Some individuals may not recognize their privileges as they have never experienced the oppressive side. Understanding privilege requires individuals to empathize and actively put themselves in other people's situations (Hofman, 2023).

Regardless, longing's potency emerges when individuals confront uncertainty regarding prospects. It transcends mere physical desires, extending deeply into emotional, metaphysical, and existential realms. Positioned within the spectrum of human drives and longing

represents a profound and enduring yearning that often shapes aspirations and existential inquiries, highlighting its significance in human experience and motivation (Ueland et al., 2018).

Ultimately, dreams are essential to our lives, propelling us toward greater heights. We aspire to what we believe will help us achieve our destiny and work hard to achieve it. For some, these goals may be small, while for others, they may be more significant and require significant effort. Our dreams keep us awake at night, and if they are not fulfilled, they can negatively affect our mental well-being (Paunikar, 2021).

Table 2. *Coping Strategies of Participants on the Challenges Encountered as Student Inmates*

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Pray because nothing is impossible for God. Think that only can help. Keep on holding to God. Read the bible. Do bible study. Trust to God. Ask for forgiveness to God. Think positive. One believes that life has still so much to offer.	Pray Unceasingly
Empower oneself. Encourage oneself. Believe that inmates can still do more extraordinary things. Never lose hope. Help other inmates. Cooperate with the given task.	
Everyone contributes when it comes to studying. Work with others peacefully. Offer help. Ask for help when needed. Strive hard for the family. Be inspired by the thought of helping one's family someday. Dream for the family. Recover some shortcomings with the family. Study the module. Do self-study. Learn every lesson in the module. Doing best to finish studying. Inmates can do better things. Leave the vices. Become a better person. Learn life lessons. Contribute to aim high to become the best version of oneself.	
	Motivate Oneself
	Collaborate with others
	Set Family as Inspiration
	Studying Hard
	Changing for the Better

Nowadays, a lot of individuals seek solace from a greater power. According to research on prayer, it may offer similar advantages to meditation in calming your nervous system and turning off your fight-or-flight reaction. You could get less irritable and irritated because of it. It was discovered that the group that engaged in spiritual meditation experienced higher reductions in anxiety and tension as well as a more upbeat mood. Many people pray; researchers believe doing so may improve mental health (Bernstein, 2020).

Technically, you must complete a task. You still need to finish it if you're not enthusiastic or motivated. You are driven to work hard to accomplish the assignment by this sense of duty since you have something you can do. You may have even volunteered for this assignment yourself rather than having it given to you, so you are eager to put in the time and effort necessary to do it. It's vital to remember that intrinsic motivation, which results from wanting to succeed and craving the inherent rewards, propels self-motivation (Ackerman, 2018).

Also, collaboration comes from another idea: two or more people cooperate to achieve a shared objective that benefits the team. Your ability to work successfully with others depends on your collaboration abilities. When individuals collaborate to achieve a shared purpose, they use their talents and experiences to solve issues, share knowledge, and contribute to achieving the objective. There are many different forms of cooperation, and leveraging your abilities to link your team can help them achieve their goals (Indeed Editorial Team, 2023).

Due to its strong relationship to one of society's core values, family inspiration is likely to include high levels of motivational arousal. But, depending on intrinsic motivation, the effect of familial inspiration on performance will probably differ. As was already established, intrinsic motivation is the urge to exert effort because you are interested in the task. Specifically, family motivation improves job performance—partially by supplying energy but not by lowering stress. Supporting a family is a significant source of

From one idea to another, every one of us has gone through these growth phases at various points in our lives and contexts. It is essential to consider what changes we can make inside ourselves to support our steps down the path, regardless of whether we ever reach a permanent condition of being "As Me" in every element of our lives. The acknowledgment of a sensation, sense, or conviction that there is something more, that there is more to being human than sensory experience, and that the larger totality of which we are a part is cosmic or divine is what it means to be spiritual (Richards, 2021; Spencer, 2012).

Therefore, parents are the ones who know the most about their children and care about them the most. Thus, parents are preferably arranged over most others to determine their kid's exceptional requirements and to settle on choices to the youngster's advantage. Having excellent parenting skills is not necessary. One cannot be flawless. No kid is flawless, either so it's crucial to remember this when we establish our standards. It is not necessary to be flawless as a parent to be successful. It does not, however, negate the need for us to make progress toward it. First and first, we should hold ourselves to the highest standards, then our kids (Diekema, 2018; Li, 2023).

Conclusion

The five participants in this study had different perspectives and experiences as student inmates due to varying lengths of incarceration. They tried to accept their circumstances, reinvent themselves, maintain happiness, and acknowledge wrongdoing. Some faced bullying and harassment, leading to feelings of exclusion. Despite being able to attend classes, they expressed frustration over the lack of resources for their studies. Nevertheless, their determination to pursue education underscores their hope for a better future and a desire to contribute positively to society. Their perseverance and adaptability highlight the profound impact that access to education can have, even within the constraints of incarceration.

Moreover, it profoundly impacted me, opening my heart and bringing awareness to the privileges I often take for granted in my own life. It has served as a reminder of my role as a mother and the significance of instilling positive values in my children. The participants' advice on initiating conversations with children to help them resist temptation resonated deeply with me. This experience has inspired me to approach parenting with renewed dedication and mindfulness. Through this study, I have gained a newfound appreciation for my children and have prioritized them even more. I am grateful to God for granting me the opportunity to conduct this research and to the participants whose insights have inspired me to become a better mother and person.

Interestingly, while investigating the experiences of student inmates, I have been genuinely inspired by them. Despite facing adversity in prison, they have found solace in knowledge and placed their trust in a higher power. Therefore, their voices have been unveiled from behind bars. Their resilience and commitment to personal growth are a powerful testament to the human spirit's ability to transcend even the most challenging circumstances. Their stories highlight the transformative potential of education and faith, offering hope and motivation for others in similar situations.

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